

FEATURES OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF THINKING OF A YOUNGER STUDENT

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ABSTRACT

This article reveals the concept of thinking, explains the types of thinking and how they function, also analyzes the thinking of a child at primary school age, highlights the features of thinking at this age and presents games for the development of a child's thinking.

Thinking is a process of cognition, which is characterized by a generalized and indirect reflection of the surrounding reality. The ancient Greek scientist and philosopher Aristotle was engaged in the study of thinking. He studied its forms, substantiated and deduced the laws of thinking. Aristotle believed that thinking is the activity of the "rational soul".

Basically, the following types of thinking are distinguished:

1. Verbal-logical.
2. Visual-figurative.
3. Visual-effective.

Verbal-logical thinking is a type of thinking that is characterized by the use of judgments and inferences. Various types of generalizations are formed and function in its structure. Verbal-logical thinking takes place entirely in the internal, mental plane. It is impossible without speech and at the same time is one of its functions.

Visual-figurative thinking is a set of methods and processes of figurative problem solving, involving a visual representation of the situation and operating with images of its constituent objects, without performing real practical actions with them.

Visual-effective thinking is thinking in which a person cognizes the world through actions with the object of cognition. The main activity of visual-effective thinking is transformative, that is, a person physically changes something around him in order to solve a problem.

The thinking of a child at the beginning of schooling is egocentric and has a special mental attitude, since he lacks the knowledge necessary to correctly solve certain problem situations. The lack of systematic knowledge and insufficient development of concepts leads to the fact that the logic of perception prevails in the child's thinking. For example, if the same amount of water, sand, or plastic changes before a child's eyes depending on the shape of the

container it is placed in, it is difficult for the child to judge that it is the same. The child becomes addicted to what he sees in a new moment when the object changes. However, by the early school age, children are already able to mentally compare individual facts, combine them into a coherent picture, and even form their own abstract knowledge in isolation from direct sources.

The development of thinking of younger students can be divided into 2 stages. The first stage covers grades 1 and 2. At this stage, the educational material is analyzed mainly in a visual-effective and visual-figurative plan. The younger student judges objects and phenomena by their external individual features. His conclusions are based on visual premises that are given in perception. Generalizations and concepts of this stage strongly depend on the external characteristics of objects and fixes those properties that lie on the surface.

At the second stage, the development of thinking of a younger student in grades 3-4 is considered. The child develops formal-logical thinking. He masters the actions of modeling, forms an analytical-synthetic type of activity and masters the classification.

The younger students are very restless. They don't know how to think logically. In the classroom, to develop their thinking, you need to use the game method. With the help of the game, it is easier for children to learn and understand information. The game really captivates the child. The more varied the games, the longer it will be possible to keep the interest of the child. Consider 3 games that will help in the development of thinking in younger students.

1. Spread out the numbers.

The game can be played in the 1st grade in a mathematics lesson when fixing the numbers. To conduct the game, the teacher needs to prepare cards with numbers from 1 to 15. You need to randomly lay out the cards on the table and ask the younger student to distribute them in descending and ascending order. At the same time, the teacher each time must remove 2-3 numbers, so the child learns to navigate and put another suitable number instead of a pass. The game can be played both with one participant and with a group. If there are two students, then you can arrange a competition for a while. The game will effectively help to consolidate counting skills.

2. The third extra.

This game will help to develop the logical abilities of schoolchildren. The task of the teacher is to correctly and competently explain the didactic material to children. In this game, students must find an extra one out of the 3 items shown in the pictures. For example: a fairy tale, a poem, a video or football, athletics, study. Students should understand which of the 3 pictures is superfluous. In this case, the video and the study will be superfluous. You can also gradually increase the number of pictures if the children are doing great.

3. Tell me from the pictures.

This game is aimed at developing speech, imagination, attention to detail, contributing to the good work of logical thinking. The game is held in a comfortable and fun environment. For the game, the teacher must prepare the material in the form of story cards in advance. Younger students should come up with a story based on three selected pictures. The task of the teacher is not to hinder the child in the story. Students should use all their imagination.

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